

Coexistence of Commercial CV-QKD in FOADM-based Metro Networks with Full or Partial C-Band Utilization

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Abstract: We assess the feasibility of deploying a commercial CV-QKD system over a 20 km amplified FOADM-based metro link, evaluating coexistence in both full and partial C-Band occupancy. Frequency allocation guidelines optimizing the performance of CV-QKD and classical channels are provided based on experiments and simulations. © 2024 The Author(s)

1. Introduction

Quantum computers can solve complex mathematical problems faster than the world's fastest supercomputers, enabling transformative business applications [1], but also presenting a security threat to telecom networks that rely on classical cryptography. Public-key based key-exchange protocols would become vulnerable, as their security relies on computational complexity assumptions. Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) offers a method to ensure secure key-exchange in the post-quantum era. Continuous-variable QKD (CV-QKD) is a suitable option for network operators due to its seamless integration with existing telecom infrastructure. CV-QKD adopts opto-electronic devices from coherent optical systems, demonstrating resilience to interference from classical channels (CC) and enabling flexible tuning of the quantum channel (QC) frequency [2, 3]. Previous works have explored the co-propagation of QC and CCs using CV-QKD research prototypes adopting discrete QPSK [4] or Gaussian modulated coherent states (GMCS) [5]. However, a significant gap remains in evaluating the feasibility of deploying commercial CV-QKD systems over existing telecom infrastructure while adhering to production network standards. In metro networks, FOADM (Fix Optical Add-Drop Multiplexer) based architectures use MUX/DEMUX devices to combine and separate CCs at transmitter (Tx) and receiver (Rx) sites, respectively, along with variable optical attenuators (VOA) and erbium-doped fiber amplifiers (EDFA) at both locations. The EDFA at the Tx site boosts the classical signal's power before it is launched into the fiber, compensating for insertion losses (IL) and ensuring effective transmission over long distances, with typical launch powers of 0 dBm per CC. At the Rx site, pre-amplification enhances the weak incoming signal before detection, ensuring effective channel detection with -6 dBm per received CC. In a previous study, we analyzed the integration of a commercial CV-QKD system into a redesigned FOADM-based metro network architecture that supports the co-propagation of QC and CCs over a 10 km fiber link [2]. In this work, we assess the feasibility of deploying CV-QKD over a 20 km amplified metro link by measuring the C-Band power bounds for coexistence considering power margin requirements of metro networks. Furthermore, we measure the minimum ASE (amplified spontaneous emission) filtering for the QC isolation to simplify the network architecture. We also evaluate the QC allocation, identifying the optimal frequencies for maximizing the CV-QKD performance in a fully occupied C-Band (39×100G/400G CCs) at the varying power of the C-Band. Finally, we analyze the impact of concentrating the total power in 8×100G CCs across different regions of the C-Band, to offer channel planning strategies for metro links when the C-Band is partially exploited. The work provides guidelines for the effective deployment of a commercial CV-QKD system in metro networks with full or partial C-Band utilization, based on experiments and simulations.

2. Experimental and Simulation Setups

Fig. 1 shows the experimental setup. The CV-QKD system is implemented with LuxQuanta's NOVA LQ® commercial platform, utilizing a true local oscillator and C-Band tunable lasers to realize the GMCS protocol. The system uses a FPGA for real-time digital signal processing, and a GPU-powered computer server runs post-processing software (error correction, parameter estimation). The system requires transmission of two channels: a QC, supporting up to 8 dB total loss, and a CC intended for key reconciliation, implemented through a TCP/IP link in the setup. The FOADM node consists of carrier-grade equipment, including a 40-channel 100 GHz MUX/DEMUX with IL measured between 4.6 dB and 5.2 dB, and EDFAs operating across a wavelength range of 1529-1561 nm, with a noise figure \leq 6.0 dB, 23 dB gain, and with a maximum output power of 20 dBm. VOAs are integrated at both sites to adjust the input power to the EDFA. The setup includes 8×100G CCs from OTN cards with fixed optics provided by the same

vendor as the optical line system, as well as $8 \times 100\text{G}$ CCs from OTN cards equipped with CFP2 modules from different providers. $6 \times 400\text{G}$ CCs from CFP2 modules plugged into whiteboxes from two vendors, all compliant with the Telecom Infra Project Phoenix specifications [6]; and $17 \times 400\text{G}$ CCs from QSFP-DD modules, with varying output power, from five providers and connected to routers from two vendors, interoperable through the 400G Open ZR+ [7] multi-source agreement. The 39 CCs are multiplexed using the MUX at FOADM Node #1. The power of the signal is amplified, then passed through a sequence of notch filters designed to mitigate ASE at 193.2 THz, corresponding to channel #32 (C32) of the 100 GHz ITU-T grid, where the QC is allocated. The OADM at the Tx combines the QC and CCs before transmitting them through a 20 km ITU-T G.652.D single-mode fiber (SMF). At FOADM Node #2, the OADM separates the QC from the CCs. The QC is detected by the QKD Rx, while the classical signal passes through a VOA, EDFA, and DEMUX. Each CC is then detected by its corresponding module via an optical loopback circuit. The measured total loss experienced by the QC due to OADMs and fiber propagation was 5.95 dB.

The simulation setup to replicate the experimental configuration is created using VPIphotonics [8]. The QKD Tx generates GMCSs through a laser, operating at 193.2 THz or 196 THz with a linewidth of 10 kHz, and using an amplitude modulator and a phase modulator. A C-band optical spectrum is considered with 39 unmodulated dummy CCs with the frequency ranges 192.1-193.1 THz and 193.3-196 THz when QC is at 193.2 THz and 192.1-195.9 THz when QC is at 196 THz. The CCs are combined with the QC using an OADM before transmission over an SMF of 10 km or 20 km. The IL at the QC in the Tx OADM is set to 0.48 dB, as per the OADM specifications. On the Rx side, the QC is dropped by the Rx OADM, with an IL of 0.57 dB, and phase-diversity detection is performed. A parameter estimation is performed to estimate the channel transmittance (T), excess noise (ξ), and asymptotic secret key fraction (r) in bits/symbol, using a reconciliation efficiency of $\beta=0.95$. T accounts for system losses, denoted by T_{ch} , and detection efficiency (η_{de}), which is 0.46 according to LuxQuanta's equipment. This results in average $T=T_{\text{ch}}\eta_{\text{de}}$ values of 0.216 for 10 km and 0.126 for 20 km. Performance is assessed in terms of ξ and secure key rate (SKR), calculated as $0.5 \times R \times r$, where 0.5 indicates that half of the quantum symbols are used for parameter estimation, and symbol rate (R) is taken as 31.25 MHz. ξ can be expressed as $\xi_0 + \xi_{\text{SpRS}} + \xi_{\text{NLI}}$, where ξ_0 represents the CV-QKD system inherent noise (set to 0.0072 SNU for 10 km and 0.005745 SNU for 20 km, in line with LuxQuanta's system), ξ_{SpRS} results from spontaneous Raman scattering (SpRS), and ξ_{NLI} represents other fiber nonlinear noise.

Fig. 1: Experimental setup, and OSA measurement (1%) of 100G/400G CC profile before Tx OADM (C-Band power: 5 dBm).

3. Results and Conclusions

Fig. 2(a) shows Luxquanta's CV-QKD performance coexisting with $39 \times 100\text{G}/400\text{G}$ CCs over distances of 10 km and 20 km. The results demonstrate that two notch filters, each providing 30 dB isolation, are sufficient to achieve ASE filtering quality comparable to seven notch filters. However, using a single notch filter proves suboptimal, leading to an average SKR reduction of 1.35 kb/s. Extending the distance to 20 km results in an average SKR reduction of 76% compared to 10 km, and secret key generation stops for classical power levels above 7 dBm, compared to nearly 10 dBm with 10 km of fiber. The excess noise at the QKD Rx is lower for 20 km, due to the strong dependence on T , which decreases with longer fiber lengths. Fig. 2(b) illustrates the performance of a selection of 100G/400G CCs (to achieve -6 dBm per CC for detection). The results show that the 100G CFP2 CCs operate below the pre-FEC BER threshold across the entire power range of -17 dBm to -8.8 dBm per CC (-1.02 dBm to 7.12 dBm of C-Band power). In contrast, the 400G QSFP-DD CCs operate at power levels above -13.5 dBm (2.41 dBm of C-Band power), while the 400G CFP2 CCs begin working at -11.46 dBm (4.45 dBm of C-Band power). Fig. 2(c) shows the impact of concentrating the power on $8 \times 100\text{G}$ CCs in different regions of the C-Band for 10 km. With sufficient guardband (GB), SpRS becomes the primary source of noise. When the QC is allocated at C32, the impact of SpRS is more pronounced with CCs allocated at higher frequencies (C53 to C60). In this scenario, the CV-QKD ceases key generation above 7.3 dBm, whereas allocating CCs at lower frequencies (C21 to C28) enables key generation above 11 dBm. The allocation of CCs on both sides of the QC (from C28 to C31 and from C33 to C36) shows similar

performance to that at lower frequencies for power levels below 6 dBm. However, above this value, the QC starts experiencing the effects of other nonlinear noise sources due to insufficient GB. Adding GB (one CC per side: CCs from C27 to C30 and from C34 to C37) improves the SKR by an average of 2.8 kb/s.

Fig. 2. (a) SKR (solid line) and excess noise (dashed line) vs. C-Band power at 10 km and 20 km with varying numbers of notch filters. (b) Pre-FEC BER vs. power per CC for 20 km. (c) SKR and excess noise vs. power concentrated in $8 \times 100\text{G}$ CCs across different regions of the C-Band. (d) Asymptotic SKR vs. C-Band power with QC allocated at C32 and C60.

Fig. 2(d) compares experimental and simulation asymptotic SKR for 20 km with 39 CCs. The maximum classical power that allows key generation is found to be 8 dBm in simulation and 7.12 dBm in experiments. Performance is slightly better in simulation due to the use of dummy channels instead of modulated channels. This graph also shows the performance for QC at C32 and C60 over a 10 km and 20 km fiber length. It highlights the improvement in SKR with respect to QC frequency allocation. As the power increases, the improvement becomes significant, reaching approximately 23% at a power level of 13 dBm for 10 km, and approximately 58% at power level of 8 dBm for 20 km because C60 is located more in the anti-Stokes region of CCs when compared with C32.

In conclusion, the results demonstrate the feasibility of deploying a commercial CV-QKD system over a 20 km metro link with full C-Band utilization. Two notch filters, each providing 30 dB isolation, effectively mitigate ASE on the QC, simplifying the network architecture. Only the 100G CFP2 meets the ± 3 dB margin required for network operations, supporting the full C-Band power range for QC operation with a margin of 8 dB (from below -1 dBm to 7 dBm). The 400G QSEFP-DD and CFP2 offer reduced margins of 4.6 dB and 2.7 dB, respectively. Allocating the QC in the anti-Stokes region (C60) is recommended in this scenario. In partial C-Band utilization, placing CCs at lower frequencies improves QC performance, and a GB is required when CCs are allocated on both sides of the QC.

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